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Bayesian Change Point Estimation of Exponentiated Inverted Weibull Distribution under Squared Error Loss Function

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Abstract

The change point estimation problem of a common change in sequence means for a very general sequence data structure is considered. The observations within each sequence are allowed to be generally dependent and non-stationary. The follow up period can be extremely short and the change point magnitudes may differ across the sequence accounting also for a specific situation that some magnitudes are equal to zero (thus, no jump is present in the sequence). We introduce Bayesian method for estimating the change point known as a Bayesian change point estimator using Natural Conjugate Inverted Gamma Prior and Squared Error Loss Function for Exponentiated Inverted Weibull Distribution. Empirical properties of the proposed estimator are investigated through a simulation study through “R” software.

Keywords: Change Point Estimation, Exponentiated Inverted Weibull Distribution Bayesian method, Natural Conjugate Inverted Gamma Prior, Squared Error Loss Function.

1.Introduction

Statistical decision theory is concerned with the making of decisions in the presence of Statistical knowledge which sheds light on some of the uncertainties involved in the decision

problem. We consider these **uncertainties** represented by unknown numerical quantities, say θ (possibly a vector or matrix).

Classical Statistics is directed towards the use of sample information (the data arising from the Statistical investigation) in making inferences about θ . These classical inferences are, mostly, made without considering the true state of parameter. In decision theory, on the other hand, an attempt is made to combine the sample information with other relevant aspects of the problem i.e. by considering the true state of parameter in form of probability model as prior distribution in order to make the best decision.

1.2. Bayesian Inference

In a Bayesian setup, the unknown parameter is viewed as random variable. The uncertainty about the true value of parameter is expressed by a prior distribution. The parametric inference is made using the posterior distribution which is obtained by incorporating the observed data into the prior distribution using Bayes theorem. Hence we update the prior distribution in the light of observed data. Thus the uncertainty about the parameter prior to the experiment is represented by the prior distribution and the same, after the experiment, is represented by the posterior distribution.

Since that the time of classical inferential procedure interest has alternated between periods of acceptance and rejection of the method as a base for the statistical inference. Often suitable and unsuspected difficulties with alternate methods of statistical inference have been largely responsible for the continued resurgence of the Bayesian method of reasoning and inferences. The method is currently riding a high tide of popularity in virtually all areas of statistical application. Jeffrey's(1961), Lindley(1965), Kendall and Stuart (1961), Box and Tiao(1973) and Savage(1954).

The Bayesian method of reasoning is much more direct that is “Deductive”. To achieve this direct approach the mean life θ is assumed to be a random variable with a priori or prior p.d.f. $g(\theta)$. This distribution expresses the state of knowledge or ignorance about θ before the sample data is analyzed. Given a prior distribution, the probability model $f(y|\theta)$ and the data y , Bayes theorem is used to calculate the so called posterior pdf $g(\theta|y)$ of Θ given data y . A distinctive feature of Bayesian Inference is that it takes explicit account of prior information in the analysis.

1.3 Loss Function

Let θ be an unknown parameter of some distribution $f(x|\theta)$ and suppose we estimate θ by some statistic $\hat{\theta}$. Let $L(\hat{\theta}, \theta)$ represent the loss incurred when the true value of the parameter is θ and we are estimating θ by the statistic $\hat{\theta}$.

The most widely used loss function in estimation problems is quadratic loss function given as $L(\hat{\theta}, \theta) = k(\hat{\theta} - \theta)^2$ where $\hat{\theta}$ is the estimate of θ , the loss function is called quadratic weighed loss function if $k=1$, we have

$$L(\hat{\theta}, \theta) = (\hat{\theta} - \theta)^2 \quad (1.3.1)$$

Known as squared error loss function (SELF).

1.4 Change or Shift Point

Physical systems manufacturing the items are often subject to random fluctuations. It may happen that at some point of time instability in the sequence of lifetimes is observed. Such observed point is known as Change or Shift point inference problem. Such Change or Shift point inference problem is useful in statistical quality control to study the Change or Shifting in process mean, Linear time series models, and models related to econometrics. The

monographs, Broemeling and Tsurmi (1987) on structural changes and survey by Zack (1981) are useful references. Bayesian approach may play an important role in the study of such Change or Shift point problem and has been often proposed as a valid alternative in classical estimation procedure. A variety of Change or Shift point problems have studied in Bayesian frame work by many authors like Zellner (1986), Calabria and Pulcini(1994) and Jani and Pandya (1999).

1.5 Exponentiated Inverted Weibull Distribution

The Inverted Weibull distribution is one of the most popular probability distribution to analyze the life time data with some monotone failure rates. Khan et al. (2008) explained the flexibility of the three parameters inverted Weibull distribution and its interested properties. Exponentiated (generalized) Inverted Weibull Distribution is a generalization to the Inverted Weibull distribution through adding a new shape parameter $\lambda \in \mathcal{R}^+$ by exponentiation to distribution function F , the new distribution function F^λ . Al-Hussaini et al (2010) explained that the cumulative distribution function is flexible to monotone and non-monotone failure rates. Mudholka et al(1995) introduced the Exponentiated Weibull Distribution as generalization of the standard Weibull Distribution, that applied the new distribution as a suitable model to the bus-motor failure time data. Nasar et al.(2003) reviewed the Exponentiated Weibull Distribution with new measures. Gupta et al.(2001) studied the Exponentiated Exponential distribution in details as an alternative distribution to Weibull distribution and Gamma distribution. Nadarajah et al (2005) discussed in details the moments of the Exponentiated Weibull distribution. Pal et al (2006) compared Exponentiated Weibull distribution with two parameters of Weibull distribution and Gamma distribution with respect to failure rate as well as some basic properties with data analysis. Gupta et al (2001) introduced Generalized Exponential distribution with different method of parameters estimation.

Mudholkar et al (1996) applied the Exponentiated Weibull distribution to the flood data with some properties. Jiang et al (1999) introduced a graphical analysis as an approach to study the parameters characterization of the Exponentiated Weibull distribution.

Recently the two parameter Exponentiated Inverted Weibull Distribution (EIW) distribution has been proposed by Flaih et al. (2012). The two parameter EIW distribution has the following probability density function

$$f(x) = \theta \beta x^{-(\beta+1)} (e^{-\theta x})^{-\beta}; \quad x > 0, (\beta > 0, \theta > 0) \quad (1.5.1)$$

And the distribution function

$$F(x) = (e^{-x^{-\beta}})^{\theta}; \quad x > 0 \quad (1.5.2)$$

Also, the reliability function of the EIW distribution with two shape parameters θ and β are given by

$$R(t) = 1 - (e^{-t^{-\beta}})^{\theta}; \quad t > 0 \quad (1.5.3)$$

1.6 Bayesian Estimation of Change point in Exponentiated Inverted Weibull Distribution under Squared Error Loss Function (SELF)

A sequence of independent lifetimes $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m, x_{(m+1)}, \dots, x_n$ ($n \geq 3$) were observed from Exponentiated Inverted Weibull Distribution with parameter β, θ . But it was found that there was a change in the system at some point of time 'm' and it is reflected in the sequence after ' x_m ' which results change in a sequence as well as parameter value. The Bayes estimate of θ and 'm' are derived for symmetric and asymmetric loss function under inverted gamma prior as natural conjugate prior.

1.6.1 Likelihood, Prior, Posterior and Marginal

Let x_1, \dots, x_n , ($n \geq 3$) be a sequence of observed discrete life times. First let observations x_1, \dots, x_n have come from Exponentiated Inverted Weibull Distribution with probability density function as

$$f(x, \beta, \theta) = \theta \beta x^{-(\beta+1)} (e^{-\theta x})^{-\beta}; \quad (x, \beta, \theta > 0) \quad (1.6.1.1)$$

Let 'm' is change point in the observation which breaks the distribution in two sequences as (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m) & $(x_{m+1}, x_{m+2}, \dots, x_n)$

The probability density function of the above sequences are

$$f_1(x) = \theta_1 \beta_1 x^{-(\beta_1+1)} (e^{-\theta_1 x})^{-\beta_1} \quad (1.6.1.2)$$

Where $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m, \theta_1, \beta_1 > 0$

$$f_2(x) = \theta_2 \beta_2 x^{-(\beta_2+1)} (e^{-\theta_2 x})^{-\beta_2} \quad (1.6.1.3)$$

; $x_{(m+1)}, \dots, x_n, \theta_2, \beta_2 > 0$

The likelihood functions of probability density function of the sequence are

$$L_1(x, \theta_1, \beta_1) = \prod_{j=1}^m f(x_j, \theta_1, \beta_1)$$

$$L_1(x, \theta_1, \beta_1) = (\theta_1 \beta_1)^m U_1 e^{-\theta_1 T_{2m}} \quad (1.6.1.4)$$

Where $U_1 = \prod_{j=1}^m x_j^{-(\beta_1+1)}$

$$T_{2m} = \sum_{j=1}^m x_j^{-\beta_1}$$

$$L_2(x, \theta_2, \beta_2) = \prod_{j=m+1}^n f(x_j, \theta_2, \beta_2)$$

$$L_2(x, \theta_2, \beta_2) = (\theta_2 \beta_2)^{n-m} U_2 e^{-\theta_2 (T_{2n} - T_{2m})} \quad (1.6.1.5)$$

Where $U_2 = \prod_{j=m+1}^n x_j^{-(\beta_2+1)}$

$$T_{2n} - T_{2m} = \sum_{j=m+1}^n x_j^{-\beta_2}$$

And the joint Likelihood function is given by

$$L(\theta_1, \theta_2 | \underline{x}) \propto (\theta_1 \beta_1)^m U_1 e^{-\theta_1 T_{2m}} (\theta_2 \beta_2)^{n-m} U_2 e^{-\theta_2 (T_{2n} - T_{2m})} \quad (1.6.1.6)$$

Suppose the marginal prior distributions of θ_1, θ_2 are natural conjugate prior

$$\pi_1(\theta_1, \underline{x}) = \frac{b_1^{a_1}}{\Gamma a_1} \theta_1^{(a_1-1)} e^{-b_1 \theta_1}; \quad a_1, b_1 > 0, \theta_1 > 0 \quad (1.6.1.7)$$

$$\pi_2(\theta_2, \underline{x}) = \frac{b_2^{a_2}}{\Gamma a_2} \theta_2^{(a_2-1)} e^{-b_2 \theta_2}; \quad a_2, b_2 > 0, \theta_2 > 0 \quad (1.6.1.8)$$

The joint prior distribution of θ_1, θ_2 and change point 'm' is

$$\pi(\theta_1, \theta_2, m) \propto \frac{b_1^{a_1}}{\Gamma a_1} \frac{b_2^{a_2}}{\Gamma a_2} \theta_1^{(a_1-1)} e^{-b_1 \theta_1} \theta_2^{(a_2-1)} e^{-b_2 \theta_2} \quad (1.6.1.9)$$

where $\theta_1, \theta_2 > 0$ & $m = 1, 2, \dots, (n-1)$

The joint posterior density of θ_1, θ_2 and m say $\pi(\theta_1, \theta_2, m | \underline{x})$ is obtained by using equations (1.6.1.6) & (1.6.1.9)

$$\rho(\theta_1, \theta_2, m | \underline{x}) = \frac{L(\theta_1, \theta_2 | \underline{x}) \pi(\theta_1, \theta_2, m)}{\sum_m \int \int_{\theta_1, \theta_2} L(\theta_1, \theta_2 | \underline{x}) \pi(\theta_1, \theta_2, m) d\theta_1 d\theta_2}$$

(1.6.1.10)

$$\rho(\theta_1, \theta_2, m | \underline{x}) = \frac{\theta_1^{(m+a_1-1)} e^{-\theta_1(T_{2m}+b_1)} \theta_2^{(n-m+a_2-1)} e^{-\theta_2(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)}}{\sum_m \int_0^\infty e^{-\theta_1(T_{2m}+b_1)} \theta_1^{(m+a_1-1)} d\theta_1 \int_0^\infty \theta_2^{(n-m+a_2-1)} e^{-\theta_2(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)} d\theta_2}$$

Assuming $\theta_1(T_{2m} + b_1) = x$ & $\theta_2(T_{2n} - T_{2m} + b_2) = y$

$$\theta_1 = \frac{x}{(T_{2m}+b_1)} \quad \& \quad \theta_2 = \frac{y}{T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2}$$

$$d\theta_1 = \frac{dx}{(T_{2m}+b_1)} \quad \& \quad d\theta_2 = \frac{dy}{T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2}$$

$$\rho(\theta_1, \theta_2, m | \underline{x}) = \frac{e^{-\theta_1(T_{2m}+b_1)} \theta_1^{(m+a_1-1)} e^{-\theta_2(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)} \theta_2^{(n-m+a_2-1)}}{\sum_m \frac{\Gamma(m+a_1)}{(T_{2m}+b_1)^{(m+a_1)}} \frac{\Gamma(n-m+a_2)}{(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)^{(n-m+a_2)}}$$

$$\rho(\theta_1, \theta_2, m | \underline{x}) = \frac{e^{-\theta_1(T_{2m}+b_1)} \theta_1^{(m+a_1-1)} e^{-\theta_2(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)} \theta_2^{(n-m+a_2-1)}}{\xi(a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, m, n)} \quad (1.6.1.11)$$

Where $\xi(a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, m, n) = \sum_{m=1}^{n-1} \left[\frac{\Gamma(m+a_1)}{(T_{2m}+b_1)^{m+a_1}} \frac{\Gamma(n-m+a_2)}{(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)^{(n-m+a_2)}} \right]$

The Marginal posterior distribution of change point 'm' using the equations (1.6.1.6), (1.6.1.7) & (1.6.1.8)

$$\rho(m|\underline{x}) = \frac{L(\theta_1, \theta_2/\underline{x}) \pi(\theta_1) \pi(\theta_2)}{\sum_m L(\theta_1, \theta_2/\underline{x}) \pi(\theta_1) \pi(\theta_2)} \quad (1.6.1.12)$$

On solving which gives

$$\rho(m|\underline{x}) = \frac{\int_0^\infty e^{-\theta_1(T_{2m}+b_1)} \theta_1^{(m+a_1-1)} d\theta_1 \int_0^\infty e^{-\theta_2(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)} \theta_2^{(n-m+a_2-1)} d\theta_2}{\sum_m \int_0^\infty e^{-\theta_1(T_{2m}+b_1)} \theta_1^{(m+a_1-1)} d\theta_1 \int_0^\infty e^{-\theta_2(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)} \theta_2^{(n-m+a_2-1)} d\theta_2}$$

Assuming $\theta_1(T_{2m} + b_1) = y$ & $\theta_2(T_{2n} - T_{2m} + b_2) = z$

$$\theta_1 = \frac{y}{(T_{2m}+b_1)} \quad \& \quad \theta_2 = \frac{z}{T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2}$$

$$d\theta_1 = \frac{dy}{(T_{2m}+b_1)} \quad \& \quad d\theta_2 = \frac{dz}{T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2}$$

$$\rho(m|\underline{x}) = \frac{\frac{\Gamma(m+a_1)}{(T_{2m}+b_1)^{(m+a_1)}} \frac{\Gamma(n-m+a_2)}{(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)^{(n-m+a_2)}}}{\sum_m \frac{\Gamma(m+a_1)}{(T_{2m}+b_1)^{(m+a_1)}} \frac{\Gamma(n-m+a_2)}{(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)^{(n-m+a_2)}}}$$

$$\rho(m|\underline{x}) = \frac{\frac{\Gamma(m+a_1)}{(T_{2m}+b_1)^{(m+a_1)}} \frac{\Gamma(n-m+a_2)}{(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)^{(n-m+a_2)}}}{\xi(a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, m, n)} \quad (1.6.1.13)$$

The marginal posterior distribution of θ_1 , using equations (1.6.1.6) and (1.6.1.7)

$$\rho(\theta_1|\underline{x}) = \frac{L(\theta_1, \theta_2/\underline{x}) \pi(\theta_1)}{\int_0^\infty L(\theta_1, \theta_2/\underline{x}) \pi(\theta_1) d\theta_1}$$

On solving which gives

$$\rho(\theta_1|\underline{x}) = \frac{\sum_m e^{-\theta_1(T_{2m}+b_1)} \theta_1^{(m+a_1-1)} \int_0^\infty e^{-\theta_2(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)} \theta_2^{(n-m+a_2-1)} d\theta_2}{\sum_m \int_0^\infty e^{-\theta_1(T_{2m}+b_1)} \theta_1^{(m+a_1-1)} d\theta_1 \int_0^\infty e^{-\theta_2(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)} \theta_2^{(n-m+a_2-1)} d\theta_2}$$

Assuming $\theta_1(T_{2m} + b_1) = y$ & $\theta_2(T_{2n} - T_{2m} + b_2) = z$

$$\theta_1 = \frac{y}{(T_{2m}+b_1)} \quad \& \quad \theta_2 = \frac{z}{T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2}$$

$$d\theta_1 = \frac{dy}{(T_{2m}+b_1)} \quad \& \quad d\theta_2 = \frac{dz}{T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2}$$

$$\rho(\theta_1|\underline{x}) = \frac{\sum_m e^{-\theta_1(T_{2m}+b_1)} \theta_1^{(m+a_1-1)} \frac{\Gamma(n-m+a_2)}{(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)^{(n-m+a_2)}}}{\sum_m \frac{\Gamma(m+a_1)}{(T_{2m}+b_1)^{(m+a_1)}} \frac{\Gamma(n-m+a_2)}{(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)^{(n-m+a_2)}}}$$

$$\rho(\theta_1|\underline{x}) = \frac{\sum_m e^{-\theta_1(T_{2m}+b_1)} \theta_1^{(m+a_1-1)} \frac{\Gamma(n-m+a_2)}{(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)^{(n-m+a_2)}}}{\xi(a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, m, n)} \quad (1.6.1.14)$$

The marginal posterior distribution of θ_2 , using the equation (1.6.1.6) & (1.6.1.8) is

$$\rho(\theta_2|\underline{x}) = \frac{L(\theta_1, \theta_2/\underline{x}) \pi(\theta_2)}{\int_0^\infty L(\theta_1, \theta_2/\underline{x}) \pi(\theta_2) d\theta_2}$$

$$\rho(\theta_2|\underline{x}) = \frac{\sum_m e^{-\theta_2(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)} \theta_2^{(n-m+a_2-1)} \int_0^\infty e^{-\theta_1(T_{2m}+b_1)} \theta_1^{(m+a_1-1)} d\theta_1}{\sum_m \int_0^\infty e^{-\theta_1(T_{2m}+b_1)} \theta_1^{(m+a_1-1)} d\theta_1 \int_0^\infty e^{-\theta_2(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)} \theta_2^{(n-m+a_2-1)} d\theta_2}$$

Assuming $\theta_1(T_{2m} + b_1) = y$ & $\theta_1 = \frac{y}{(T_{2m}+b_1)}$

$$\rho(\theta_2|\underline{x}) = \frac{\sum_m \frac{\Gamma(m+a_1)}{(T_{2m}+b_1)^{(m+a_1)}} e^{-\theta_2(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)} \theta_2^{(n-m+a_2-1)}}{\sum_m \frac{\Gamma(m+a_1)}{(T_{2m}+b_1)^{(m+a_1)}} \frac{\Gamma(n-m+a_2)}{(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)^{(n-m+a_2)}}$$

$$\rho(\theta_2|\underline{x}) = \frac{\sum_m \frac{\Gamma(m+a_1)}{(T_{2m}+b_1)^{(m+a_1)}} e^{-\theta_2(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)} \theta_2^{(n-m+a_2-1)}}{\xi(a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, m, n)} \quad (1.6.1.15)$$

1.6.2 Bayes Estimators under Squared Error Loss Function (SELF)

The Bayes estimate of a generic parameter (or function there of) θ based on a SELF is given by

$L_1(\theta, d) = (\theta - d)^2$, where 'd' is a decision rule to estimate θ , is posterior mean. For the change point 'm' which is a non negative integer quantity $m = 1, 2, \dots, (n-1)$ the loss function is defined as

$$L_1(m, \hat{m}_s) = (m - \hat{m}_s)^2 \quad (1.6.2.1)$$

Where $\hat{m}_s = 1, \dots, (n-1)$, is the smallest integer greater than analytical solution.

The Bayes estimate \hat{m}_{BS} of 'm' under SELF using marginal posterior density equation

$$(1.6.1.13) \text{ is given as } \hat{m}_{BS} = \sum_m m \rho(m|\underline{x})$$

$$\hat{m}_{BS} = \frac{\sum_m m \frac{\Gamma(m+a_1)}{(T_{2m}+b_1)^{(m+a_1)}} \frac{\Gamma(n-m+a_2)}{(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)^{(n-m+a_2)}}}{\xi(a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, m, n)} \quad (1.6.2.2)$$

Bayes estimate $\hat{\theta}_{1BS}$ of θ_1 under SELF using marginal posterior density equation (1.6.1.14) is given by

$$\hat{\theta}_{1BS} = \int_0^{\infty} \theta_1 \rho(\theta_1 | \underline{x}) d\theta_1$$

On simplification which gives

$$\hat{\theta}_{1BS} = \frac{\sum_m \frac{\Gamma(n-m+a_2)}{(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)^{(n-m+a_2)}} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\theta_1(T_{2m}+b_1)} \theta_1^{(m+a_1)} d\theta_1}{\xi(a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, m, n)}$$

Assuming $\theta_1(T_{2m} + b_1) = y$ & $\theta_1 = \frac{y}{(T_{2m}+b_1)}$

$$\hat{\theta}_{1BS} = \frac{\sum_m \frac{\Gamma(n-m+a_2)}{(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)^{(n-m+a_2)}} \frac{\Gamma(m+a_1+1)}{(T_{2m}+b_1)^{(m+a_1+1)}}}{\xi(a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, m, n)}$$

$$\hat{\theta}_{1BS} = \frac{\xi[(a_1+1), a_2, b_1, b_2, m, n]}{\xi(a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, m, n)} \quad (1.6.2.3)$$

Bayes estimate $\hat{\theta}_{2BS}$ of θ_2 under SELF using marginal posterior density equation (1.6.1.15)

is given by

$$\hat{\theta}_{2BS} = \int_0^{\infty} \theta_2 \rho(\theta_2 | \underline{x}) d\theta_2$$

$$\hat{\theta}_{2BS} = \frac{\sum_m \frac{\Gamma(m+a_1)}{(T_{2m}+b_1)^{(m+a_1)}} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\theta_2(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)} \theta_2^{(n-m+a_2)} d\theta_2}{\xi(a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, m, n)}$$

Assuming $\theta_2(T_{2n} - T_{2m} + b_2) = y$ & $\theta_2 = \frac{y}{(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)}$

$$\text{Then } \hat{\theta}_{2BS} = \frac{\sum_m \frac{\Gamma(m+a_1)}{(T_{2m}+b_1)^{(m+a_1)}} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-y} \frac{y^{(n-m+a_2)}}{(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)^{(n-m+a_2)}} \frac{dy}{(T_{2n}-T_{2m}+b_2)}}{\xi(a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, m, n)}$$

$$\hat{\theta}_{2BS} = \frac{\xi[a_1, (a_2+1), b_1, b_2, m, n]}{\xi(a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, m, n)} \quad (1.6.2.4)$$

1.7. Numerical Comparison for Exponentiated Inverted Weibull Sequences

We have generated 20 random observations from Exponentiated Inverted Weibull distribution with parameter $\theta = 2$ and $\beta = 0.5$. The observed data mean is 1.5616 and variance is 0.6812.

Let the change in sequence is at 11th observation, so the means and variances of both sequences

(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m) and $(x_{(m+1)}, x_{(m+2)}, \dots, x_n)$ are $\theta_1 = 1.5491$, $\theta_2 = 1.5769$ and $\sigma_1^2 = 1.0197$

and $\sigma_2^2 = 1.0197$. If the target value of θ_1 is unknown, its estimating ($\hat{\theta}_1$) is given by the mean of first m sample observation given m=11, $\theta = 1.54$.

Table 1.1. Numerical Comparison for Exponentiated Inverted Weibull Sequences

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1.3764	0.9956	1.2049	1.0227	1.0973	1.5452	1.3607	1.3996	1.0366	4.5379
11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
1.4629	1.4163	0.9498	2.2346	1.3364	2.6647	1.6726	0.9039	1.8044	1.2094

Now again we have generated the random samples of different sizes say 10, 20, 30. Obviously the Change or Shift point occurs between 1 to 20 i.e. say 11. and calculated the Bayes estimates under squared error loss function by making programs in R-language, again repeating these steps for 1000 times we have calculated the M.S.E. by making program in R and then analyze the data and given the conclusions.

1.8. Sensitivity Analysis of Bayes Estimates

In this section we have studied the sensitivity of the Bayes estimates with respect to changes in the parameters of prior distribution a_1, b_1, a_2 and b_2 . The means and variances of the prior distribution are used as prior information in computing these parameters. Then with these parameter values we have computed the Bayes estimates of m, θ_1 and θ_2 under squared error loss function (SELF) considering different set of values of (a_1, b_1) and (a_2, b_2) . We have also considered different sample sizes n=10(10)30. The Bayes estimates of the change point 'm' and the parameters θ_1 and θ_2 are given in table-2.2 under SELF. Their respective mean squared errors (M.S.E's) are calculated by repeating this process 1000 times and presented in same

table in small parenthesis under the estimated values of parameters. All these values appear to be robust with all values of prior parameter values *and* all sample size. From the below table we conclude that -

The Bayes estimates of the parameters θ_1 and θ_2 of EIW obtained with SELF are seems to be efficient as the numerical values of their mse's are very small for $\hat{\theta}_{1BS}$ and $\hat{\theta}_{2BS}$ in comparison with \hat{m}_{BS} . The Bayes estimates of the parameters are robust uniformly with all values of prior parameters as and all sample size.

Table 1.2, Bayes Estimates of m , θ_1 & θ_2 for EIW sequences and their respective M.S.E.'s Under SELF

(a_1, b_1)	(a_2, b_2)	n	\hat{m}_{BS}	$\hat{\theta}_{1BS}$	$\hat{\theta}_{2BS}$
(1.25,1.50)	(1.50,1.60)	10	4.8555 (6.6156)	1.5339 (0.0768)	1.4304 (0.3208)
		20	8.8815 (5.0083)	1.4429 (0.2993)	1.4939 (0.3546)
		30	10.7302 (4.3495)	1.4587 (0.3713)	1.9662 (0.2742)
(1.50,1.75)	(1.70,1.80)	10	5.1221 (7.6881)	1.8187 (0.0408)	1.5001 (0.3435)
		20	8.5352 (1.9036)	1.2948 (0.5223)	1.9424 (0.0553)
		30	11.2492 (2.7492)	1.2058 (0.3142)	1.6401 (0.0478)
(1.75,2.0)	(1.90,2.0)	10	4.7124 (3.7767)	1.3386 (0.3319)	1.4244 (0.2549)

		20	9.4625 (5.5862)	1.4846 (0.4221)	1.8507 (0.6915)
		30	21.4869 (3.4512)	2.4034 (0.3406)	1.1456 (0.1006)
(2.0,2.25)	(2.10,2.20)	10	5.1169 (4.6495)	1.4848 (0.2337)	1.1686 (0.2605)
		20	9.7756 (4.5228)	1.9437 (0.2667)	1.8657 (0.4126)
		30	15.3401 (8.4773)	1.7141 (0.0854)	1.6222 (0.5717)
(2.25,2.50)	(2.30,2.40)	10	5.7097 (5.1637)	1.7736 (0.1237)	1.2112 (0.3548)
		20	10.0649 (28.4202)	1.7118 (0.0117)	1.8381 (0.0257)
		30	15.7377 (77.6218)	1.5959 (0.0898)	1.3582 (0.0594)
(2.50,2.75)	(2.50,2.60)	10	4.4010 (4.4734)	1.3659 (0.3783)	1.7129 (0.1262)
		20	11.7454 (37.1136)	1.6919 (0.1851)	1.4569 (0.2749)
		30	17.0312 (69.6320)	2.1408 (0.2010)	1.6705 (.0460)

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